

Assessment of Genetic Variability among Advanced Potato (*Solanum tuberosum* L.) Genotypes at Bekoji, Southeastern Ethiopia

*Demis Fikre¹, Kedir Jalet¹, Gizaw Wegayehu¹, Dasta Tsagaye¹ and Nimona Fufa¹

¹Ethiopian Institute of Agricultural Research, Kulumsa Agricultural Research Center, Asela, Ethiopia

*Corresponding author: [Demis Fikre](#)

Ethiopian Institute of Agricultural Research, Kulumsa Agricultural Research Center, Asela, Ethiopia

Abstract

Potato is one of the most important crops grown in the cool highlands of Arsi, Ethiopia. This study aimed to evaluate the nature and magnitude of genetic variability among potato genotypes concerning tuber quality, yield, and yield-related traits under the agro ecological conditions of Bekoji, Ethiopia. The experiments were conducted during the main growing season of 2022 to 2023 using RCBD with three replications. The results showed highly significant differences ($P \leq 0.01$) among the tested potato genotypes for all evaluated traits, except days to emergence, days to maturity, and unmarketable tuber yield. The interaction effects of genotype \times year demonstrated the presence of highly significant differences for all studied traits except days to emergence, days to maturity, plant height, and unmarketable yield. The analysis of tuber yield result showed significant variation among evaluated genotypes, with the yields ranging from 39.42 t ha⁻¹ (G6) to 62.2 t ha⁻¹ (G4). While most genotypes exhibited variable performance across two seasons, G4, G11, and G1 demonstrated stable yield consistency across two cropping seasons. The genotypic and phenotypic coefficient of variations was estimated to the range from 0.0% to 43.3% and 5.14% to 51.43% respectively. Correspondingly, late blight severity exhibited high phenotype and genotypic variance highlighting the substantial potential for selection to improve these traits. Heritability estimates ranged from 0.0% to 79%, with days to emergence and plant height showing the lowest and highest heritability, respectively. Overall, the study demonstrated significant genotypic variability among the tested genotypes, providing a promising opportunity for selecting genotypes with higher yields and improved resistance to late blight. Medium genotypic and phenotypic coefficient of variation was observed for traits such as plant height and average stem number. In contrast, the lowest genotypic and phenotypic coefficient of variation observed for days to emergence, days to 50% flowering, days to 50% maturity, dry matter content, specific gravity, marketable yield, unmarketable yield, and total yield, indicated that selection-based on those traits is not effective in yield improvement. Estimate of heritability in a broad sense ranged from 0.0% to 79% for traits of days to emergence and plant height respectively. The study revealed that the presence of genotypic variability in tested genotypes indicated a higher chance of selecting genotypes with high yield and resistance to late blight.

Keywords: Genetic advance; Heritability; Potato variability, Stability; Tuber yield.

1. Introduction

Potato (*Solanum tuberosum* L.) is a tuber crop that produces more yields per unit area than any other crop on the planet. It is a key economic crop all over the world. Potatoes are the third most important food crop for human consumption after rice and wheat, and they feed over a billion people (FAOSTAT, 2022). China, India, and the United States account for more than 80% of global potato production, whereas Africa accounts for only approximately 5% (FAOSTAT 2022). The human population in Ethiopia is increasing, so enhancing the productivity of potato crops is critical for the country's food security.

Potato is grown in more than 150 countries, a staple food of about one billion people in the world about half is localized in developing countries (Anonymous, 2019). Globally, more than one and more billion people eat potatoes as a staple

food (Ahmed *et al.*, 2018, Chen *et al.*, 2021). Global potato production has increased by about 20% since 1990, although production is still 50% below that of wheat, maize, and rice (Anonymous, 2019). It is produced for fresh potato tubers in about 359 mt from a total area of 16.5 million hectares (Anonymous, 2020). In Ethiopia, it ranks first among root and tuber crops. Potato is characterized as a cheap and nutritious food security crop (Beals, 2019). Potatoes are very rich in various nutrients such as carbohydrates, amino acids, vitamins, minerals, antioxidants, dietary fibers, and protein (Burgos *et al.*, 2020).

The genetic makeup, crop maturity, agronomic practices, environmental conditions, storage temperatures, pests, and diseases are the major factors that affect tuber yield. Studying the genetic variability present among different potato genotypes for a given character is a basic precondition to designing systematic breeding methods (Engida *et al.*, 2007; Arslanoglu *et al.*, 2011). Genotypic improvement of potato varieties through hybridization and selection across environments and seasons is the basic strategy for researchers to the increment of tuber yield. The more diverse parents from the population, the more the chance of improving the traits under consideration. Therefore, the selection of better crossing materials from the germplasm is crucial, so the presence of sufficient and desirable genotypic variability among genotypes and heritable traits must exist. Strategic potato research in Ethiopia began in 1975 with the understanding of the constraints challenging its production and productivity (Baye and Gebremedhin, 2013).

The development and dissemination of more than 36 (Belete, Gudanie, Dagim, and Jalene...) improved varieties, coupled with other technological packages, contributed greatly to the improvement and rapid expansion of potato production (MANR, 2016). The major objective of potato breeding has been to develop potato cultivars that have maximum yield potential, adaptable to wide agro-ecologies and resistant to late blight which has been the most devastating disease throughout the dominant potato-producing highlands of the country (Wassu, 2016).

Most smallholder farmers in Ethiopia still cultivate low-yielding table and processing varieties. Local and previously released/improved varieties are becoming less productive and more prone to serious disease as the climate has begun to change. Enhancing potato yield and other desirable qualities through crossing could help generate high-yielding varieties for the wide range of environments in Ethiopia, as well as varieties adapted to future environments as the climate changes. A sustained increase in yield is required for food security in a nation undergoing substantial human population growth (Bradshaw, 2006). Among the main challenges causing this low potato productivity limited number of improved and high-yielding potato varieties adapted to current biotic and abiotic stresses worsened by the current climate changes (Rukundo *et al.*, 2019). The primary goal of the current study was to assess the nature and magnitude of genetic variability in potato genotypes for tuber quality, yield, and yield-related traits at Bekoji.

2. Materials and Methods

2.1 Planting materials and testing locations

The field experiment was conducted at Bekoji testing locations during the 2022 and 2023 main cropping seasons (June–November). Bekoji is the major potato-growing area in the Arsi zone of the Oromia region which is about 237 km apart from Addis Ababa. The soil composition in the study areas is primarily clay, which is acidic in nature, a characteristic that can influence plant growth and pest behavior. The agro-climatic conditions in this region are classified as wet, with an average annual rainfall of 1020 mm. The rainfall pattern follows a uni-modal distribution, with the majority of the precipitation occurring from March to September. The peak rainy season, which is crucial for crop development, spans from June to August, providing the necessary moisture for agricultural activities. Detailed information about the locations is described in Table 1 below.

Table 1: Description of experimental locations

Location	Latitude	Longitude	Altitude	Mean annual rainfall	T ^o		Soil type
					Min	Max	
Bekoji	0732'37"N	3915'21"E	2780	1020	7.9	18.6	clay

Min = minimum, Max = maximum temperature. Source: Kulumsa Agricultural Research Center, Bekoji Meteorology station, 2022 & 2023.

Experimental materials

Fifteen advanced potato genotypes including one standard check (Burka) were evaluated. Detailed information about the experimental materials is described in Table 2 below.

Table 2: Lists of evaluated potato experimental materials (genotypes)

No.	Treatments	Status	No.	Treatments	Status
1	CIP315003.25	Advanced clone	9	CIP315004.61	Advanced clone
2	CIP315009.70	Advanced clone	10	CIP315003.83	Advanced clone
3	CIP315003.132	Advanced clone	11	CIP315003.166	Advanced clone
4	CIP315008.182	Advanced clone	12	CIP315010.161	Advanced clone
5	CIP315008.160	Advanced clone	13	Burka	Registered variety
6	CIP315008.154	Advanced clone	14	CIP315004.13	Advanced clone
7	CIP315004.113	Advanced clone	15	CIP315009.30	Advanced clone
8	CIP315009.71	Advanced clone			

The experimental designs and field trial management

The trial was conducted using a randomized complete block design with three replications used to evaluate the selected fifteen genotypes along with standard checks (Table 2). The plot sizes are 3m in length and 3m in width, which is 9m² areas. The spacing between rows was 75 cm, and the spacing between individual plants within the rows was 30 cm, which is a common practice for optimizing plant growth and minimizing competition for nutrients and light.

For each replicate, a total of forty (40) plants were planted in four-row plots, ten plants per row. This arrangement allowed for sufficient plant density to assess the genotypic variations effectively, while also ensuring each plant had enough space to grow without excessive competition. To prevent late blight disease, a fungicide (Redomil Gold MZ 68 WG) was sprayed once during the cropping season. Other crop husbandry techniques were conducted in accordance with national recommendations. All other crop management practices, including fertilization, and pest control, were carried out in accordance with national agricultural recommendations, ensuring that the trial adhered to standard best practices for potato cultivation in the region.

2.2 Data collected

In the national variety trial, a comprehensive set of data was collected to assess various traits related to disease, phenology, growth yield components and quality traits. These observations were made from the plants located in the two central rows of each plot, which were deemed representative for accurate measurements. For yield components, the harvested tubers were categorized in two groups: unmarketable and marketable. Unmarketable tubers included those that were very small, malformed, or diseased, while marketable tubers were defined as healthy, well-formed tubers with a diameter greater than 20 mm. The marketable yield was calculated using just marketable tubers, but the total tuber yield was calculated using both marketable and unmarketable tuber yield. To determine dry matter content a representative sample of 200 g marketable tubers per genotype was taken from test site and replication and cleaned, dried in a dry oven, and then weighed. A specific gravity was determined by using five kg of potato tubers weight in air-weight in water method. Tubers were first weighted in air and then weighted submerged in water (Kleinkopf and Wassermann, 1987).

2.3 Statistical analysis

The statistical analysis of variance (ANOVA) for combined data over seasons was calculated using R software version 4.4.0. The following RCBD models were used for combined analysis.

$$Y_{ij} = \mu + G_i + E_j + GE_{ij} + \beta(E)_{jk} + \varepsilon_{ijk}$$

Where; Y_{ij} is the grain yield of the i^{th} genotype in the j^{th} year, μ = the grand mean, G_i = the effect of the i^{th} genotype, E_j = the effect of the j^{th} year, GE_{ij} = the interaction of the i^{th} genotype with the j^{th} year, (E) = the effect of the k^{th} replication in the j^{th} year, and ε_{ijk} = the error.

2.3.1 Estimation of genetic parameters

The genetic parameters (genotypic variance, phenotypic variance, H^2b , GCV, PCV, GA and GAM) were estimated using the following equations;

$$\sigma^2g = \frac{MSG - MSG * l}{rl}, \quad \sigma^2g * l = \frac{MSG * l - MSe}{r}, \quad \sigma^2p = \sigma^2g + \frac{\sigma^2p}{rl} + \frac{\sigma^2g * l}{l},$$

$$PCV = \frac{\sqrt{\sigma^2p}}{\bar{x}} * 100, \quad GCV = \frac{\sqrt{\sigma^2g}}{\bar{x}} * 100, \quad H^2b = \frac{\sigma^2g}{\sigma^2p} * 100,$$

$$GA = K * \sqrt{\sigma^2p} * H^2b, \quad GAM = \frac{GA}{\bar{x}} * 100$$

Where, σ^2g =genotypic variance, σ^2e =environmental variance, σ^2p = phenotypic variance, MSg =mean square due to genotypes, MSe =error mean square, r =number of replication, $MSg*l$ =mean square due to genotypes X location, l =number of environment, PCV =phenotypic coefficient of variation, GCV =genotypic coefficient of variation, H^2b = heritability in broad sense, GA =genetic advance, K =Selection differential at 5 % selection intensity which accounts to a constant value 2.063, GAM =genetic advance as percent of mean, \bar{X} = population Mean.

2.3.2 Estimation of genotypic and phenotypic correlation coefficient

The phenotypic and genotypic associations of tuber yield per hectare with other agronomic traits were estimated using the following function of R software;

$$\text{Phenotypic correlation coefficient (r}_{pxy}) = \frac{Pcovxy}{\sqrt{(\sigma^2_{px})(\sigma^2_{py})}}$$

$$\text{Genotypic correlation coefficient (r}_{gxy}) = \frac{Pcovxy}{\sqrt{(\sigma^2_{px})(\sigma^2_{py})}}$$

3. Results and Discussion

3.1 ANOVA results

The analysis of variance (ANOVA) for 11 quantitative traits across 15 genotypes revealed highly significant differences ($P \leq 0.01$) for most traits, except days to emergence, days to maturity, and unmarketable tuber yield. These significant variations highlight the considerable genetic diversity present among the potato genotypes for the majority of the traits examined. Such diversity is essential for breeding programs, as it provides a broader genetic base for selecting genotypes with desirable traits such as improved yield, disease resistance, and better adaptability to various environmental conditions. Many authors also reported the existence of significant variation among genotypes for different traits. Demelie and Argaw (2016), Getachew et al. (2016) and Ebrahim et al., (2023) reported highly significant differences among genotypes for plant height, average tuber number per plant, average tuber weight, dry matter content, and total tuber yield. Furthermore, interaction effects of genotype \times year showed the presence of highly significant differences for all studied traits except days to emergence, days to maturity, plant height and unmarketable yield (Table 3). This suggests that the performance of potato genotypes varies substantially across different growing seasons, highlighting the influence of environmental factors such as climate, soil conditions, and year-specific stressors on genotype expression. For most traits, this variation across years indicates that certain genotypes may perform better in one season but not in another, emphasizing the dynamic nature of genotype-environment interactions. This finding underscores the importance of evaluating genotypes across multiple cropping seasons to fully understand their potential and stability in diverse environmental conditions.

Table 3: Mean square from the analysis of variance of 11 traits for combined analysis result

Traits	Entry (14)	Year (1)	Rep:Year(4)	Entry:Year(14)	Residuals (56)
DTE	2.029	98.178***	4.622	2.13	3.706
DTF	25.78***	413.88***	8.41	11.73*	5.02
DTM	75.4	4825.3***	153.1	87.8	75.7
PLH	507.77***	440.9*	106.27	109.13	78.25
ASN	5.998***	36.354***	1.495	2.283*	1.063
DRM	10.0178**	4.7426	1.6074	6.4874*	3.3157
SPG	0.000225**	0.000107	0.000036	0.000146*	0.000074
LBT	66.538***	274.576***	7.303	19.322***	5.112
MRY	341.4**	6794***	13.9	288.7*	127.3
UMRY	5.2615	25.9882*	9.2574	2.8383	4.9038
TYLD	356**	5979.6***	45.5	284.7*	130.2

DTE = days to emergency, *DTF* = days to 50% flowering, *DTM*= days to maturity, *PLH*= plant height, *ASN*, average stem number, *DRM*= dry mater content, *SPG* = specific gravity, *LBT*= Late blight, *MRT*= marketable tuber yield, *UMRY*= unmarketable tuber yield, *TYLD*= total tuber yield.

Table 4: Combined mean performances of 11 traits on potato genotypes

Gen	DTE	DTF	DTM	PLH	ASN	DRM	SPG	LBT	MRY	UMRY	TYLD
G1	14.2	68.8f-h	111.3a-c	66.9g	4.5cdef	20.3c-e	1.1c-e	10.1b	35.8e	3.6a-c	39.4d
G2	14	69.2e-h	113.3a-c	68.8g	4.2def	20.7b-d	1.1b-d	15.7a	39.1c-e	3.8a-c	42.9cd
G3	14.7	73.7a-c	116a-c	72.3fg	5.9b	21.7a-d	1.1a-d	6.6d-f	37.9c-e	5.2ab	43.1cd
G4	14.5	74a	118.7ab	82.3b-f	5.4bc	22.2a-c	1.1a-c	3.9g-i	57.6a	4.6a-c	62.2a
G5	14.3	68.5gh	115.5a-c	88.8bc	5.4bc	18.3e	1.1e	5.9d-g	55.2ab	6.2a	61.3a
G6	13.7	70.2d-g	114.7a-c	86.3bd	5.9b	20.5b-d	1.1b-d	4.6e-i	47.7a-e	4.2a-c	52a-d
G7	14	73.8ab	118.5abc	77d-g	4.8bcde	23.7a	1.1a	3.3hi	54.9ab	3.4bc	58.3ab
G8	13.8	73.2a-c	108.5c	79.6c-f	4.9bcde	22.4ab	1.1ab	5.8d-h	36.4de	3.9abc	40.3cd
G9	13.5	71.2c-f	116.7a-c	76e-g	4.1def	22.2a-c	1.1a-c	10.1bc	43.8b-e	3.5bc	47.3b-d
G10	15	67.3h	117abc	81.5b-f	4.8bcde	21.5b-d	1.1b-d	5.4d-i	49.8a-c	2.3c	52.1a-d
G11	15.3	71.2c-f	120ab	85.8be	3.9ef	21.9a-d	1.1a-d	4.7e-i	54.8ab	3.2bc	58ab
G12	14.3	71.3b-f	120.8a	80c-f	3.5f	20de	1.1de	7.5cd	37.3c-e	3.6bc	40.8cd
G13	14	71.7a-e	118.5abc	103a	5.2bcd	22.4ab	1.1ab	3i	47.6a-e	4.6a-c	52.2a-d
G14	13.3	71.2c-f	114.7a-c	91b	7.5a	21.4b-d	1.1b-d	4f-i	48.9a-d	4.5a-c	53.4a-c
G15	13.3	72.7a-d	110.7bc	76.6d-g	5.8b	22.1a-c	1.1a-c	6.7de	48.3a-e	3.2bc	51.5a-d
CV (%)	12.58	3.15	7.52	10.91	20.38	8.35	0.75	34.92	23.61	53.20	22.18
LSD	2.2ns	2.59	10.08	10.23	1.19	2.11	0.009	2.61	13.03	2.56	13.19

LSD (5%), least significant difference, ns= non-significant difference, CV (5%) = coefficient of variation in percent, DTE = days to emergency, DTF = days to 50% flowering, DTM= days to maturity, PLH= plant height, ASN, average stem number, DRM= dry mater content, SPG = specific gravity, LBT= Late blight, MRT= marketable tuber yield, UMR= unmarketable tuber yield, TYLD= total tuber yield.

3.2 Mean performance of genotypes

The combined mean performances of tuber yield across two seasons of 15 potato genotypes were presented in Table 5. The analysis mean yield result showed the presence of significant variation among genotypes, with yields ranging from 39.42 t ha⁻¹ for G6 to 62.2 t ha⁻¹ for G4. This range indicates that there are substantial differences in how each genotype responded to the growing conditions in both seasons. The variation in yield is likely influenced by genetic factors, as well as environmental factors that may have fluctuated across the two seasons, such as temperature, rainfall, soil health, and pest pressure.

While most genotypes showed different performance across the two seasons, indicating a degree of environmental sensitivity, genotypes G4, G11, and G1 stood out for their consistent and stable yield performance. These genotypes demonstrated an ability to maintain high yields regardless of the seasonal variations, which makes them promising candidates for selection in breeding programs focused on developing potato varieties with stable performance across different environmental conditions. The stability observed in G4, G11, and G1 suggests these genotypes may possess inherent resilience or adaptability traits that allow them to perform well across diverse growing conditions, which is a highly desirable characteristic for any crop variety meant for large-scale production.

Table 5: Mean tuber yield performances of potato genotypes across 2022 and 2023

No-	G-code	Genotype	Bekoji-2022	Bekoji-2023	Mean
1	G1	Burka	52.09	50.94	51.51
2	G2	CIP-315003.25	57.39	46.98	52.18
3	G3	CIP-315008.154	49.97	56.79	53.38
4	G4	CIP315003.132	62.65	61.75	62.20
5	G5	CIP315003.166	60.92	24.90	42.91
6	G6	CIP315003.83	48.61	30.23	39.42
7	G7	CIP315004.113	45.66	36.00	40.83
8	G8	CIP315004.13	55.53	39.06	47.30

9	G9	CIP315004.61	74.09	41.88	57.98
10	G10	CIP315008.160	77.89	44.77	61.33
11	G11	CIP315008.182	52.67	51.26	51.96
12	G12	CIP315009.30	65.31	38.86	52.08
13	G13	CIP315009.70	45.31	35.26	40.28
14	G14	CIP315009.71	74.05	42.58	58.31
15	G15	CIP315010.161	54.94	31.29	43.12

G = genotypes

3.3 Estimation of genetic parameters

3.3.1 The Genotypic and Phenotypic Coefficient of Variation

The variability components including genotypic and phenotypic variance, heritability in a broad sense, and genetic advance as a percentage of mean, genotypic and phenotypic variance were estimated for eleven characters, and results are presented below in Table 6. The genotypic and phenotypic coefficient of variations (GCV and PCV) was calculated in the range between 0.0% to 43.3% and 5.14% to 51.43% respectively. These coefficients reflect the extent of variability observed within the genotypes for each trait. GCV and PCV values are generally categorized into high, moderate, and low levels based on their percentages: values above 20% are considered high, those between 10% and 20% are moderate, and values below 10% are low (Deshmukh et al., 1986).

The analysis revealed that traits with high GCV and PCV values are more likely to respond to selection, meaning there is significant potential for improvement through breeding. Correspondingly, late blight severity exhibited high phenotype and genotypic variance indicating greater scope of selection for the improvement of these characters. This suggests that late blight severity is a trait where selection could lead to meaningful improvements in disease resistance in future breeding programs. On the other hand, medium genotypic and phenotypic coefficient of variation values was recorded for traits like plant height and average stem number, indicating moderate variability for these traits. This suggests that these traits may also offer some potential for improvement through selection, though the scope for genetic gains might be more limited compared to traits with high GCV and PCV values.

In contrast the lowest genotypic and phenotypic coefficient of variation values were observed for traits such as days to emergence, days to 50% flowering, days to 50% maturity, dry matter, specific gravity, marketable yield, unmarketable yield, and total yield. These low values suggest that these traits exhibit relatively little variability among the genotypes, making them less responsive to selection. As a result, focusing on these traits for improving yield is likely to be less effective, as genetic gains in these areas may be minimal. This highlights the importance of targeting traits with higher genetic variability when aiming for significant improvements in yield and other key agronomic characteristics.

Table 6: Estimates of genetic parameters for 11 traits

Trait	GV	PV	H	GA	GAM	GCV (%)	PCV (%)	CV
DTE	0.00	0.53	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	5.14	12.58
DTF	2.34	4.30	0.54	2.33	3.27	2.15	2.91	3.15
DTM	0.00	13.61	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	3.19	7.52
PLH	66.44	84.63	0.79	14.90	18.38	10.05	11.35	10.91
ASN	0.62	1.00	0.62	1.28	25.26	15.56	19.77	20.38
DRM	0.61	1.67	0.36	0.97	4.53	3.64	6.03	8.35
SPG	0.00	0.00	0.36	0.00	0.42	0.34	0.56	0.78
LBT	7.87	11.09	0.71	4.88	75.29	43.32	51.43	34.92
MRY	8.78	56.90	0.15	2.40	5.18	6.40	16.28	23.61
UMRY	0.13	0.88	0.15	0.28	7.10	9.00	23.51	53.20
TYLD	11.87	59.33	0.20	3.18	6.32	6.85	15.31	22.18

DTE = days to emergency, DTF = days to 50% flowering, DTM= days to maturity, PLH= plant height, ASV, average stem number, DRM= dry mater content, SPG = specific gravity, LBT= Late blight, MRT= marketable tuber yield, UMRY= unmarketable tuber yield, TYLD= total tuber yield.

3.3.2 Heritability and Genetic advance

In this study, high heritability values were found for traits such as plant height and late blight severity, with estimates indicating that genetic factors largely control the expression of these traits, with relatively low influence from environmental factors. A high heritability value suggests that phenotypic performance is a good indicator of genetic potential, and thus, direct phenotypic selection could be effectively employed to improve these traits. This means that breeding efforts focusing on these traits are likely to result in measurable genetic gains over time, as the environment has a minimal impact on the expression of these traits. Similar findings were reported by Tesema *et al.*, (2022) and Ebrahim *et al.*, (2023) for plant height, tuber yield, average tuber number, dry matter content, and specific gravity. In contrast to this finding, high estimates of heritability were reported for days to emergence; marketable tuber, late blight severity and total tuber yield (Ali *et al.*, 2021), further reinforcing the idea that trait with high heritability values can be more effectively improved through direct selection. Overall, the high heritability for certain traits in this study supports the notion that these traits are genetically controlled and can be improved more efficiently through breeding strategies that emphasize selection based on phenotypic expression.

Moderate heritability in broad sense was observed from average stem number, and days to 50% flowering. Moderate heritability suggests that these traits are influenced by both genetic factors and environmental factors to a certain extent, meaning that while there is genetic variation, environmental conditions still play a significant role in the expression of these traits. This level of heritability implies that while selection based on phenotypic performance can be somewhat effective, there will still be a considerable impact from environmental factors, which might make it more challenging to achieve substantial genetic gains through selection alone. The observed results were in agreement to Ebrahim *et al.*, (2023) for average tuber weight. On the other hand, the lowest estimate of heritability was observed for marketable yield, unmarketable yield, total yield, dry matter, and specific gravity. These traits demonstrated a high degree of environmental influence, indicating that phenotypic variation in these traits is largely driven by external factors such as soil fertility, climate, and agricultural practices rather than by genetic factors alone. As a result, selection based solely on phenotypic performance may not lead to significant genetic improvements in these traits. In summary, the moderate to low heritability observed for these traits indicates that for traits with high environmental influence, such as yield-related traits and dry matter content, breeders should be cautious when relying purely on phenotypic selection.

Genetic advance as percent of mean ranged from 0.0% – 14.9%, reflecting the potential for improvement through selection for various traits in the studied potato genotypes. Johansen *et al.* (1955) classified genetic advances as a percentage of the mean (GAM) as high (>20%), moderate (10–20%) and low (<10%). According to this benchmark, plant height recorded moderate genetic advance, indicates that the possibility to select the genotypes with better performance for these traits. While, all other evaluated agronomic traits observed lower genetic advance as percent of mean.

Pearson's correlation analysis

The correlation values explain the apparent association of the crop yield or plant structure, with each other and clearly indicated the magnitude and directions of the association and relationships. These correlations provide important information for selecting traits that could contribute to improvements in potato cultivation. Analysis of correlation between variability parameters for tuber yield is shown in Fig. 1. One of the key findings is the positive and highly significant correlation between dry matter content and days to flowering ($r = 0.67^{**}$), indicating that as the time to flowering increases, the dry matter content tends to be higher. This suggests that later-flowering genotypes may allocate more energy to the development of dry matter in their tubers, which could be an advantageous trait for improving tuber quality in certain breeding programs. However, dry matter content was negatively and non-significantly correlated with late blight disease ($r = -0.38$), suggesting that while there is a relationship between these two traits; it is not strong enough to make meaningful predictions or draw definitive conclusions. This indicates that the expression of late blight disease is not directly predictably influenced by dry matter content, or that other factors are contributing to disease susceptibility. Total tuber yield was significantly correlated with plant height ($r=0.52^*$), meaning that taller plants tend to produce higher tuber yields. This relationship could be valuable for selecting taller genotypes that have the potential for higher yield, although the strength of the correlation indicates that other factors, such as tuber size and number, also contribute to yield. There was also a very strong and positive association between total tuber yield and marketable tuber yields (0.99^{***}), which strongly suggests that increasing total yield generally leads to a corresponding increase in marketable yield, making it a crucial target for improving overall productivity.

On the other hand, late blight disease showed negatively and highly significant correlated with to plant height (-0.70^{**}), indicating that shorter plants tend to be more resistant to late blight, or that taller plants may be more susceptible to the disease. This negative correlation also extended to marketable yield ($r = -0.60^*$) and total yield ($r = -0.60^*$), suggesting that increased late blight severity is associated with reduced yields. The negative relationship between late blight and yield traits emphasizes the importance of selecting for resistance to late blight in breeding programs, as reducing the severity of the disease could help mitigate yield losses. In summary, the correlation analysis highlights important

relationships between yield-related traits and plant structure, with clear implications for breeding strategies. The strong positive associations between marketable yield and total yield, as well as the negative impact of late blight on yield, provide valuable insights for identifying genotypes that can achieve both high yield and disease resistance. Additionally, the relationships between dry matter content and days to flowering suggest potential avenues for improving tuber quality in breeding efforts.

Figure 1. Correlation of different traits included. Abbreviations are as presented under Table 4.

4. Conclusion

The experiment on potato genotypes showed the presence of highly significant ($p < 0.01$) among genotypes for most evaluated traits and it indicates the presence of sufficient amount of genetic variability among populations. This variability is crucial as it supports the potential for efficient selection and improvement of potato varieties. The presence of higher genotypic and phenotypic coefficient of variation helps in the selection of better parent materials in the development of better varieties.

Most of the traits have scored medium to low GCV and PCV values, indicating that while they may have some variability, their potential for improvement through selection might be more limited compared to traits with higher

variability. This highlights the importance of focusing on traits with higher genetic variation for achieving faster and more significant improvements in potato breeding.

In conclusion, the findings from this experiment emphasize the importance of evaluating potato genotypes across location and growing seasons to obtain a more comprehensive understanding of their performance and genetic parameters. The environmental variability across location and seasons can significantly influence genotype performance, and assessing genotypes under various conditions can provide a more accurate estimate of their true potential. Therefore, we recommend conducting individual evaluations of potato genotypes across multiple locations and growing seasons. This approach will not only lead to better estimates of genotype performance but also enhance the reliability and effectiveness of selection for the development of superior, high-yielding, and disease-resistant potato varieties.

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Author Contributions

All authors contributed to the idea and design of the study. Demis Fikre completed the initial draft of the manuscript, arranged the materials, and conducted the data analysis. The data collecting and planting were assisted by all other authors. Each author offered criticism on earlier iterations of the work. Thus, all authors read, revised, and approved the manuscript.

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